

Studies on some Divalent Metal Complexes of 2,3-Substituted-benzofuran Derivatives†

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The complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with 3-amino-2-benzofurancarbonitrile (L) and 3-amino-2-benzofuranthiocarboxamide (L') have been prepared and characterised on the basis of elemental analyses, molar conductance, magnetic moment, electronic and infrared spectral data. The various ligand field parameters like Dq , B' , LFSE etc. have been evaluated for Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes which suggest an octahedral geometry for each of them. Infrared spectral data indicate a polymeric distorted octahedral structure for Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes with the exception for Hg^{II} complex of the latter ligand which may have a tetrahedral geometry.

BENZOFURAN derivatives are known to possess high analgesic, analeptic, antiviral and antiinflammatory activities¹⁻⁴. Consequently the metal complexes of 2,3-substituted-benzofuran derivatives is a subject of great biological interest. However, only a limited information is available on the metal complexes of such derivatives. In continuation to our earlier work^{5,6}, we report here the complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} metal ions with 3-amino-2-benzofurancarbonitrile (L) and 3-amino-2-benzofuranthiocarboxamide (L'). These

L, R=CN
L', R=OSNH₂

complexes has been characterised by chemical analyses and conductivity, magnetic moment, uv-visible and ir spectral studies.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of AnalaR grade. The ligands L and L' were synthesised by the known procedures⁷.

Complexes with ligand L: To a hot concentrated ethanolic solution of the ligand, a solution of metal chloride in 1:1 (metal-ligand) molar ratio (1:2 ratio in case of Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes) in a small amount of the same solvent was added. The resulting mixture was refluxed for 1-2 h. The solution was further concentrated whereupon Cu^{II} complex separated out. In the case of other complexes, the solid sodium acetate was added to facilitate precipitation. The resulting mixture was treated

with an excess of petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) to isolate the complex as a solid. For Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes, the reaction mixture was treated with acetone instead of petroleum ether. The solid complexes thus obtained were filtered, washed with ethanol in portions and dried in vacuum over fused calcium chloride.

Complexes with ligand L': A hot aqueous solution of metal chloride was treated with a hot solution of the ligand in aqueous ethanol (50%) in 1:1 (metal-ligand) molar ratio (1:2 ratio in case of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes). The reaction mixture was stirred magnetically on a hot-plate for 2 h. At room temperature the complex separated out on scratching the walls of the container. In the case of Ni^{II} complex, the solid sodium acetate was added to raise the pH, and at room temperature the solution was treated with solvent ether to get the complex precipitated. The solid complexes were filtered washed with aqueous ethanol and dried in vacuum over fused calcium chloride.

The details of elemental analyses and the physico-chemical techniques employed for magnetic measurements, electronic and infrared spectra are the same as described in the earlier papers^{5,6}.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are stable. They are soluble to a limited extent in DMF and DMSO and insoluble in common organic solvents, except $\text{HgL}'\text{Cl}_2$ which is soluble in nitrobenzene, chloroform and acetonitrile. The analytical data (Table 1) indicate 1:1 (metal-ligand) stoichiometry for Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of L and Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes of L', whereas the rest of the complexes show 1:2 stoichiometry. All the complexes of L' have low values of molar conductance (4.5-20.7

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} B.M.
		M	N	Cl	S	
CoLCl ₂	265	20.75 (20.46)	9.60 (9.72)	24.16 (24.66)	—	4.94
NiLCl ₂	300	20.66 (20.40)	9.66 (9.73)	24.56 (24.68)	—	2.89
CuLCl ₂	300	21.89 (21.70)	9.81 (9.57)	24.02 (24.27)	—	1.88
ZnL ₂ Cl ₂	300	14.29 (14.46)	12.14 (12.38)	15.78 (15.69)	—	—
CdL ₂ Cl ₂	300	21.78 (22.51)	11.08 (11.21)	14.55 (14.22)	—	—
HgL ₂ Cl ₂	300	34.41 (34.14)	9.40 (9.59)	12.31 (12.08)	—	—
NiL'Cl ₂	300	18.16 (18.25)	8.64 (8.70)	21.80 (22.07)	9.52 (9.95)	3.3
CuL'Cl ₂	205	19.05 (19.45)	8.31 (8.57)	21.97 (21.74)	9.97 (9.80)	1.6
ZnL ₂ 'Cl ₂	300	12.34 (12.57)	10.47 (10.76)	13.51 (13.64)	12.38 (14.30)	—
CdL ₂ 'Cl ₂	300	19.75 (19.81)	9.53 (9.87)	12.21 (12.51)	11.39 (11.28)	—
HgL'Cl ₂	160	43.52 (43.27)	6.99 (6.04)	15.13 (15.31)	6.59 (6.90)	—

$\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) in DMF solution ($\sim 10^{-3} M$) suggesting them to be non-electrolytes⁹. For the complexes of L, the molar conductance could not be determined due to their limited solubility in DMF.

The effective magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) (Table 1) for CoLCl₂ falls in the range 4.7–5.1 B.M. expected for high-spin octahedral geometry⁹. The μ_{eff} values for Ni^{II} complexes are well within the range expected for six-coordinated Ni^{II} complexes¹⁰. For CuLCl₂, the magnetic moment is 1.88 B.M. suggesting an octahedral nature; whereas 1.6 B.M. observed for CuL'Cl₂, is consistent with one unpaired electron. However, the low value of the latter may be due to spin-orbit coupling through super-exchange phenomenon¹¹.

The solid state spectra (nujol) of CoLCl₂ (Table 2) is characterised by the appearance of a broad band at 8 695 cm⁻¹ and another band at 18 180 cm⁻¹ assignable to ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{2g}(F) (ν_1) and ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{1g}(P) (ν_2) transitions, respectively, in a distorted octahedral environment¹². The ligand field parameters Dq , B' and β are calculated from the assigned band positions of ν_1 and ν_2 by using the relations¹³, $Dq = [(2\nu_1 - \nu_2) + (\nu_2^2 + \nu_1\nu_2 - \nu_1^2)^{1/2}]/20$, and $B' = (\nu_2 - 2\nu_1 + 10Dq)/15$. These results point out to a distorted octahedral geometry around the central metal atom. The ν_3 band due to ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴A_{2g}(F) transition could not be observed, as it is a two-electron process and is much weaker than the other two transitions. Therefore, ν_3 transition remains almost unobserved because of its weakness and proximity to a strong ν_2 transition¹⁴. However, the value of ν_3 band has been calculated ($\nu_3 = \nu_1 + 10Dq$) which is in good agreement with Tanabe–Sugano diagram for d⁷ ion in an octahedral environment, where ν_2 and ν_3 transitions are predicted to lie almost at the same position¹⁵. The pink coloured CoLCl₂ dissolves to a limited extent in DMF and the solution slowly changes to blue colour which may be due to the change of configuration from a polymeric octahedral to a monomeric tetrahedral species¹⁶. The solid state (nujol) electronic spectra of Ni^{II} complexes exhibit two broad bands in the range 8 700–8 900 and around 15 000 cm⁻¹ attributed to the ligand field bands ν_1 and ν_2 , corresponding to the transitions ³A_{2g}→³T_{2g}(F) and ³A_{2g}→³T_{1g}(F), respectively. The third band ν_3 (³A_{2g}→³T_{1g}(P) transition) appears as a shoulder around 26 500 cm⁻¹ on a sharply rising uv absorption tail of the charge transfer band. The spectra of both the Ni^{II} complexes are typical of their octahedral geometry¹². The Racah parameter B' values for NiLCl₂ and NiL'Cl₂ calculated by using the diagonal sum rule¹⁷ are less than the free-ion value 1 040 cm⁻¹, suggesting a considerable

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA FOR Co^{II}, Ni^{II} AND Cu^{II} COMPLEXES

Compd.	λ_{max} cm ⁻¹	Dq cm ⁻¹	B' cm ⁻¹	β	β^0 %	ν_2/ν_1	LFSE kcal mol ⁻¹
CoLCl ₂	ν_1 8 695 ν_2 18 455* ν_3 18 180	976	703	0.73	27.3	2.12	16.17
NiLCl ₂	ν_1 8 890 ν_2 15 270 14 815* ν_3 26 670	889	988	0.93	6.46	1.72	30.48
CuLCl ₂	13 500 25 000 C.T.	1 350	—	—	—	—	23.14
NiL'Cl ₂	ν_1 8 695 ν_2 14 890 14 510* ν_3 26 825	870	988	0.931	6.85	1.71	29.80
CuL'Cl ₂	14 300 26 000 C.T.	1 430	—	—	—	—	24.51

* Calculated value.

orbital overlap. The experimental and calculated¹⁸ values of ν_2 band are in good agreement, suggesting an octahedral geometry. A broad asymmetric band in the region 13 500–14 300 cm^{-1} is observed in the solid state (nujol) electronic spectra of Cu^{II} complexes. The broadness of the band may be due to Jahn–Teller distortion. Duff *et al.*¹⁹ suggested that the absorption bands in this region are due to tetragonally distorted octahedral environment around Cu^{II} ion. However, the recent studies²⁰ on electronic spectra of Cu^{II} complexes indicate that the three transitions, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, $\rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and $\rightarrow {}^2E_g$ are close in energy and often give rise to a single broad absorption envelop.

The bands observed at 3 460 and 3 170 cm^{-1} are ascribed to asymmetric and symmetric NH_2 (thioamide) stretching modes²¹, respectively, in the ir spectra of free L' . These bands remain unaltered or show a slight blue-shift in the respective complexes suggesting non-involvement of NH_2 group in coordination. The medium intensity bands observed in the region 3 480–3 250 cm^{-1} are assigned to NH_2 group (primary amine) in both the ligands. These are shifted to higher frequencies in all the complexes of L , suggesting non-involvement of amino group in coordination, except for CuLCl_2 where a negative shift of about 30–50 cm^{-1} appears suggesting participation of amino group in bonding. In all the complexes of L' , the primary amine bands show red-shift, except for $\text{NiL}'\text{Cl}_2$ suggesting the involvement of NH_2 group in coordination, whereas in the latter complex these bands show blue-shift indicating no coordination. An intense band observed at 2 250 cm^{-1} for L is assigned to $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ stretch²¹. This band shows red-shift with considerable decrease in intensity on complexation indicating the coordination of the nitrogen atom of nitrile group in all the complexes. The decrease in intensity of the band may be due to decrease in bond order of $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ ²¹. The ligand L' exhibits bands of medium intensity in the regions 1 565–1 395, 1 335–1 245 and 1 130–1 020 cm^{-1} assignable to NCS–thioamide bands I, II and III, respectively²². In the respective metal complexes, these frequencies show slight red-shifts suggesting coordination through sulphur atom. The thioamide band IV mainly due to $\text{C}=\text{S}$ stretch²² observed at 778 and 760 cm^{-1} in the ligand, shifts to 760–715 cm^{-1} with reduced intensity in all the complexes. The ir spectra of both the ligands exhibit strong to medium intensity bands in the region 1 225–1 125 cm^{-1} assignable to $\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$ stretching vibrations of furan ring²⁴. On complex formation, these frequencies decrease with reduced intensity in the case of $\text{NiL}'\text{Cl}_2$ and all the complexes of L except for CuLCl_2 complex. In the rest of the complexes, the $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}}$ shows slight blue-shift or remain unaltered. These observations clearly indicate the coordination of furan oxygen in the former and not in the latter complexes. The involvement of furan oxygen in bonding in the case of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes of L and $\text{NiL}'\text{Cl}_2$ is further

supported by the appearance of new non-ligand bands in the far-ir region 530–510 cm^{-1} attributable to $\text{M}-\text{O}$ (furan oxygen) stretch²⁵. The weak intensity bands observed in the region 465–320 cm^{-1} are ascribed to $\text{M}-\text{N}$ stretch²⁶ in all the complexes except for $\text{NiL}'\text{Cl}_2$. The bands observed in the region 380–275 cm^{-1} are attributed to $\text{M}-\text{S}$ stretch²⁷ in all the complexes of L' . The bands observed in the region 295–240 cm^{-1} for Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of ligand L and Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Co^{II} complexes of ligand L' have been assigned to $\text{M}-\text{Cl}$ terminal vibrations, and bands in the region 250–225 cm^{-1} to $\text{M}-\text{Cl}$ bridging vibrations in view of their polymeric nature. In rest of the complexes, the bands in the range 290–230 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\text{M}-\text{Cl}$ terminal vibrations²⁸.

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